

UNDERSTANDING NEURODEGENERATIVE DISEASE PATHOLOGY: A GUIDE FOR GENERAL NEUROLOGISTS

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Abstract: Neurodegeneration involves the progressive dysfunction or loss of selectively vulnerable neurons in the brain and spinal cord. Despite significant advancements in fluid and imaging biomarkers, the definitive diagnosis of most neurodegenerative diseases still depends on neuropathological examination. Careful clinicopathological correlation has been instrumental in shaping clinical diagnostic criteria, enhancing our understanding of disease progression, and uncovering conditions with substantial public health relevance, such as variant Creutzfeldt-Jakob disease, iatrogenic amyloid- β deposition, and chronic traumatic encephalopathy. Neuropathological analysis can also reveal previously undetected genetic conditions with potential implications for family members. Additionally, detailed postmortem tissue examination plays a vital role in research aimed at uncovering molecular mechanisms of neurodegeneration and developing or validating biomarkers. This review highlights the hallmark pathological features of neurodegenerative diseases commonly encountered in general neurology, including Alzheimer's disease and Parkinson's disease; rarer but recognized disorders like progressive supranuclear palsy, corticobasal degeneration, and multiple system atrophy; as well as emerging entities such as chronic traumatic encephalopathy and age-related tau astroglial pathology.

Keywords: Neurodegenerative diseases, proteinopathies, amyloid- β ($A\beta$), tau protein, α -synuclein, transactive DNA-binding protein 43 (TDP-43), prion proteins, Alzheimer's disease (AD), Parkinson's disease (PD), dementia with Lewy bodies (DLB).

Introduction

Adult-onset neurodegenerative diseases are commonly classified as proteinopathies, as they are characterized by the misfolding of native peptides and proteins, such as amyloid- β ($A\beta$), tau, α -synuclein, transactive DNA-binding protein 43 (TDP-43), and prion proteins. These misfolded proteins assemble into larger filaments, which subsequently aggregate into morphologically distinct cellular inclusions or extracellular parenchymal plaques (Figure 1). More than 50 diseases are linked to protein misfolding pathology, including well-established conditions like Alzheimer's disease (AD) and Parkinson's disease (PD), as well as newly recognized entities with uncertain clinical significance, such as age-related tau astroglial pathology (ARTAG) and limbic-predominant age-related TDP-43 encephalopathy (LATE).

In most neurodegenerative diseases, misfolded protein pathology spreads topographically through synaptically connected brain regions, with distinct conformations of the same misfolded protein causing specific patterns of regional and cellular vulnerability. Additionally, pathology may arise in situ due to cell-intrinsic factors, such as high metabolic demand or genetic risk factors—including somatic mutations—that increase the susceptibility of certain neurons to protein misfolding. Regardless of the underlying mechanism, clinical manifestations are largely dictated by the anatomical distribution of neuropathology. Consequently, similar clinical phenotypes can result from different proteinopathies.

This phenotypic overlap often makes accurate diagnosis during life challenging, and neuropathology remains the gold standard for definitive diagnosis. Systematic brain banking and clinicopathological correlation have been fundamental to establishing diagnostic criteria for major neurodegenerative diseases, ensuring consistency and accuracy in clinical practice.

A Practical Guide to Neuropathological Diagnosis of Neurodegenerative Diseases

The neuropathological diagnostic process begins with macroscopic examination, typically after weighing the brain. The dura, leptomeninges, and cerebral vasculature are inspected for lesions or surface abnormalities, including gyral atrophy patterns. The hemispheres are then separated along the midline. In brain bank settings, one hemisphere is generally fixed in formalin for sectioning, while the other is dissected fresh and flash-frozen.

The formalin-fixed hemisphere is dissected systematically. The brainstem and cerebellum are removed first, followed by slicing the hemisphere coronally, the cerebellum sagittally, and the brainstem transversely. This process allows for the identification of focal or diffuse pathology, such as regional atrophy or depigmentation of the substantia nigra and locus coeruleus.

Approximately 20 brain regions are routinely sampled for histological analysis, with additional regions examined based on the clinical history or observed macroscopic abnormalities. This detailed and systematic approach ensures a thorough assessment, aiding in the accurate diagnosis and understanding of neurodegenerative diseases.

Established Clinicopathological Diseases

Alzheimer's Disease (AD)

AD is the most prevalent neurodegenerative disease, typically presenting as an amnesic syndrome. However, less common phenotypes include posterior cortical atrophy, behavioral and dysexecutive syndromes, logopenic variant primary progressive aphasia, and corticobasal syndrome. Although the majority of AD cases are sporadic, 5–10% of early-onset cases (occurring before 65 years) are linked to identifiable autosomal dominant mutations in the *presenilin (PSEN1 and PSEN2)* or *amyloid precursor protein (APP)* genes, or APP duplication.

The possibility of iatrogenic transmission of amyloid- β ($A\beta$) neuropathology has been recognized, particularly in cases where high levels of $A\beta$ were found in individuals who died of iatrogenic Creutzfeldt-Jakob disease decades after receiving cadaver-derived human growth hormone. This has raised concerns about potential $A\beta$ transmission during medical procedures involving contaminated dura mater grafts or neurosurgical instruments.

Macroscopic Features

In typical amnesic presentations, cortical atrophy is most pronounced in multimodal association cortices and medial temporal structures, particularly the hippocampus and amygdala. In contrast, the primary motor and somatosensory cortices are relatively spared. Additionally, loss of neuromelanin pigmentation in the locus coeruleus is a common macroscopic finding.

Histological Features

AD is considered a mixed proteinopathy due to the presence of both misfolded $A\beta$ and tau proteins within neuritic plaques. Initially, extracellular $A\beta$ plaques are diffuse but mature over time to form dense central cores. According to the amyloid-cascade hypothesis, these plaques initiate tau aggregation in surrounding dystrophic neurites, resulting in the formation of neuritic plaques. Mutations in *APP*, *PSEN1*, and *PSEN2*, which affect $A\beta$ metabolism, are

linked to early-onset AD, whereas mutations in the *MAPT* gene, which causes primary tauopathies, do not lead to AD.

Phosphorylated tau aggregation is a hallmark histological feature of AD. Tau initially accumulates in neuronal bodies as pretangles, which mature into neurofibrillary tangles and, following cell death, persist as ghost tangles. While A β plays a role in initiating tau misfolding, clinical features and the extent of cortical atrophy correlate more strongly with tau pathology density than with A β burden.

The spread of neuropathology in most cases of AD follows the Braak and Braak model, beginning in the medial temporal lobe structures and progressively extending to neocortical areas. Exceptions include limbic-predominant and hippocampal-sparing subtypes.

The neuropathological diagnosis of AD is guided by the National Institute on Aging-Alzheimer's Association (NIA-AA) guidelines. This involves semi-quantitative assessments of:

1. Regional A β pathology (Thal phase)
2. Regional neurofibrillary tangle presence (Braak and Braak stage)
3. Cortical neuritic plaque density (CERAD score)

These parameters collectively estimate the likelihood of dementia being attributable to AD neuropathological changes.

Synucleinopathies

Synucleinopathies are neurodegenerative diseases characterized by the pathological aggregation of α -synuclein protein. They can be divided into two main pathological entities:

1. **Lewy Body Disease:** This includes Parkinson's disease (PD) and dementia with Lewy bodies (DLB). These disorders are akinetic-rigid syndromes distinguished by the timing of dementia onset. In PD, dementia typically occurs more than one year after the onset of motor symptoms, while in DLB, cognitive decline precedes or coincides with motor symptoms. Despite this clinical distinction, PD and DLB are likely part of the same clinicopathological spectrum.
2. **Multiple System Atrophy (MSA):** MSA commonly presents with autonomic dysfunction and either cerebellar ataxia (MSA-C) or parkinsonism (MSA-P). While PD has numerous monogenic causes (e.g., *SNCA*, *PRKN*, *PINK-1*, *DJ-1*, *VPS35* mutations) and susceptibility genes (e.g., *LRRK2*, *GBA*), MSA is primarily sporadic. However, G51D mutations in the *SNCA* gene can lead to combined α -synucleinopathy, exhibiting neuropathological features of both PD and MSA.

Macroscopic Examination

- **PD and DLB:** Key findings include pallor and atrophy of the substantia nigra and locus coeruleus, often accompanied by varying degrees of frontal and medial temporal lobe atrophy.
- **MSA:** Atrophy extends beyond the substantia nigra, involving olivopontocerebellar (OPCA) or striatonigral (SND) regions, which correspond to MSA-C and MSA-P clinical subtypes, respectively. Rarely, in minimal-change MSA, atrophy is confined to the substantia nigra despite widespread α -synuclein pathology.

Histological Examination

- **PD and DLB:** Both are characterized by the accumulation of α -synuclein fibrils in neurons, forming Lewy bodies and Lewy neurites. The progression of Lewy pathology typically follows a caudal-to-rostral pattern, as described by Braak and colleagues, spreading from the brainstem through the limbic regions to the neocortex. Recent studies have

identified amygdala-predominant and olfactory-restricted patterns of Lewy pathology. At the microscopic level, PD and DLB cannot be distinguished at autopsy, as the electron cryo-microscopy structures of α -synuclein filaments are identical in both conditions.

- **MSA:** α -synuclein aggregation occurs in both neurons and oligodendrocytes, forming neuronal and glial cytoplasmic inclusions. Less frequently, inclusions are found in the nuclei of glial cells and neurons. While Lewy pathology may be present in 10–20% of MSA cases, the structure of α -synuclein filaments in MSA is distinct from that observed in PD/DLB.

This distinction between Lewy body disease and MSA highlights the variability in clinical presentation and pathology across the synucleinopathies, reflecting differences in the structure and distribution of α -synuclein aggregates.

Conclusion

Neuropathological examination remains the definitive gold standard for diagnosing most neurodegenerative diseases. Beyond diagnosis, it holds significant implications for the relatives of affected individuals and broader public health. Emerging pathological entities continue to require detailed clinicopathological correlation, underscoring the dynamic nature of this field. Advances in molecular biology techniques further reinforce the value of neuropathological studies, even for well-characterized conditions like Alzheimer's disease (AD) and Parkinson's disease (PD). Such examinations are vital for advancing high-quality research into the molecular mechanisms underlying these diseases and for the discovery and validation of tissue-based biomarkers.

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